

Problems of investing China in the Kyrgyz Republic

Sherbekova Anara Amankulovna, Ph.D. in Economics, Professor
Abdyldaeva Umut Maratovna, PhD in Economics, Associate Professor
Wang Qiang, undergraduate

Kyrgyz State University of Construction, Transport and Architecture named after N. Isanov,
Bishkek, Kyrgyz Republic

Annotation. The article studies the trends of China's investment in the Kyrgyz Republic, as well as the problems associated with investing in the Kyrgyz Republic. The net FDI inflows from China and the Kyrgyz Republic are analyzed. In recent years, China has been a leader in investment in the Kyrgyz Republic. Moreover, the external debt of the Kyrgyz Republic more than half consists of funds from China, which would adversely affect the financial security of the Kyrgyz Republic in the future.

Keywords: investment, China, economy, external debt, international relations, foreign direct investment

Various international relations are largely characterized by the level of investment ties. Depending on the economic situation of the country, the need for foreign material, financial, labor and other resources is recognized by all world states. Significant investments in the Kyrgyz Republic from non-CIS countries come mainly from China and Turkey. So, in the last 3 years (2016-2018), the PRC has been a leader in terms of direct investment inflows in the Kyrgyz Republic, exceeding this indicator in 2018, compared to 2014, by 52.6%. At the same time, the share of Chinese FDI in total direct investment revenues is, on average, 37.3%. This suggests that the People's Republic of China is the largest investor in Kyrgyzstan.

Basically, direct foreign investment is carried out by creating joint economic entities. According to statistical sources, in 2018, 446 Chinese and 193 joint Kyrgyz-Chinese enterprises operated in the Kyrgyz Republic. As can be seen from the figure, the number of operating enterprises with investments from China has a tendency to increase, while with the full participation of Chinese capital from 2014 to 2018 by 2 times. It should be noted that 2983 enterprises with Chinese capital are registered. Chinese business in the Kyrgyz economy is rapidly expanding its presence. Basically, such enterprises are small, and large and medium ones are practically absent. At the same time, these enterprises recruit workers exclusively from the Chinese.

One of the problems in providing jobs is that the majority of workers in all joint ventures are Chinese. According to information from the State Migration Service under the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic, in 2018, the largest number of permits to attract foreign labor were received by Chinese citizens – more than 74.7% or 9670 foreign specialists [1,6].

In addition to the labor sphere, companies from China often do not comply with environmental, technical norms and rules when the latter conduct entrepreneurial activities in Kyrgyzstan. So, based on information from various government agencies, including the Prosecutor General's Office of the Kyrgyz Republic [3], the State Service for Combating Economic Crimes

of the Kyrgyz Republic [4], the State Inspectorate for Environmental and Technical Safety [2], etc. facts of violation by the Chinese business of the current legislation of the Kyrgyz Republic:

- In 2018, the gold mining company of China LLC Full Gold Mining dismissed more than 400 employees, and 370 employees of the enterprise refused to renew labor contracts when the company's management determined new conditions that reduce wages by 30%. By these actions, Full Gold Mining LLC violated the Labor Code of the Kyrgyz Republic prohibiting worsening the working conditions of workers.

- In 2018, a corruption scandal broke out in connection with the modernization of the Bishkek CHP carried out by the Chinese company TBEA. The proposal of the latter did not meet the interests of Kyrgyzstan because of its high cost, technological and technical shortcomings.

- In 2019, as a result of the actions of the Chinese coal mining company Jin Long LLC, seven villages in the south of the Kyrgyz Republic were left without a single source of fresh water.

The above facts apply to fairly large entities with the participation of Chinese capital. Offenses by small enterprises and individual citizens of the PRC also have a place to be.

All of the above creates the problems of doing Chinese business in the Kyrgyz Republic. This is especially true for building relations between entrepreneurs from China and the local population of the republic. Our small analysis allows us to express the opinion that anti-Chinese sentiments have a certain basis. If China pursues a policy of encouraging its citizens to migrate abroad, thereby solving not only its own internal problems of overpopulation, but also increasing its influence in the region, for a small Kyrgyzstan, an uncontrolled flow of labor resources of a foreign state, while maintaining high unemployment, represents a certain threat. Thus, it must be said that both the Kyrgyz Republic and the PRC need to do a lot of work to prevent negative factors that impede the mutually beneficial economic and political cooperation of these states.

References:

1. State Migration Service under the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic [Electronic resource]: official. website: [electron. text data.](http://ssm.gov.kg/отчеты/) - Bishkek, 2020. - Access mode: <http://ssm.gov.kg/отчеты/>.

2. State Inspectorate for Environmental and Technical Safety under the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic [Electronic resource]: official. website. - Bishkek, 2020. - Access mode: <http://geti.gov.kg/novosti.html>.
3. General Prosecutor's Office of the Kyrgyz Republic [electronic resource]: the official. Website: - Bishkek, 2020. - Access mode: <https://www.prokuror.kg/poisk.html?q=news>.
4. State Service for Combating Economic Crimes under the Government of the Kyrgyz Republic [Electronic resource]: official. website. - Bishkek, 2020. - Access mode: <http://www.finpol.gov.kg/ru/news>
6. Dzhumakadyrov, S. Migrants from China made the government think about it [Electronic resource]: officer. website: electron. text data. - Bishkek, 2019. - Access mode: <https://rus.azattyk.org/a/27758564.html>.